

Risk Register Revival: Preservation Planning in a Time of Change

The management of a digital archive requires the ability to audit and interrogate digital formats for a variety of archival functions. Some examples where format analysis work can be useful are Transfers advice, digitisation format selection and format migration for preservation or access purposes. The National Archives of Australia uses the 'performance model' as a guideline for digital archiving decisions that means the archive strives to preserve the meaningful content of archival records rather than only focusing on preserving the original format. In 2022 The National Archives developed a File format register and risk matrix for digital file formats as part of a broader strategy to holistically manage the digital collection. This register was created to centralise management of a dispersed and varied collection that is held across multiple systems. The risk matrix has been evaluated and updated by a newly formed team and the file format register and reporting process is undergoing current uplift made possible by system and data connectivity improvements.

Background: A Risk Framework for Digital Formats

The National Archives accepts and seeks to actively and openly manage risk in all its activities.

In 2022 the Preservation section developed A Risk Framework for Digital records to support both organisational capability and preservation planning. The Framework was designed to work with the National Archives Risk Management Guide to ensure alignment with risk approaches at an organisational level. It also incorporated aspects of the ABC method of Risk Assessment developed by the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM), and the risk management cycle described by ISO 31000:2009 Standard for Risk Management. The approach sought to incorporating high level collection risk assessment using tools the Digital Preservation Coalition RAM (Rapid Assessment Model) as well as developing an in-house risk assessment matrix to engage with assessing formats in the collection to inform preservation planning.

Review: Identified areas for improvement Format Register

The original format register was created to manage and prioritise preservation for a digital collection that is described and held across multiple systems and locations. It has a section to include both internal and external format risk assessments and identification methods including the PRONOM register and NARA's format evaluations and planning. The triage section was taking too much staff time and required streamlining and areas of the register used for reporting were now able to be improved in light of a large scale Archives-wide project improving and unifying collection data.

Risk Framework

The National Archives Risk framework initially included a two tiered approach to managing format risk. For all formats in the collection, the format register includes a quick internal triage risk assessment using a series of questions focusing on internal requirements as well as space to include external risk assessments for formats by peer organisations. The second tier was a more complex for detailed technical assessments to support preservation requirements that may include preferred formats for migration for preservation.

Achievements so far

- The file format risk triage tool in the register has been streamlined and the new layout tested for more consistent results
- The pathway to more detailed technical research and preservation planning has been clarified and is being incorporated into ongoing digital archiving workflow uplift
- The data management and reporting aspects of the format register have been separated for improvement in collaboration with ICT systems teams.
- The team has started to link this work with preservation planning for specific electronic record types such as datasets or emails.

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Future Plans

The review of the current format register has highlighted the importance of system and data connectivity to informed management

- Develop data plan to automate and push format reporting and visibility into archive systems and out of excel
- Build workflows to link and adapt format evaluations to different archiving contexts
- Build internal consistency with file format decision making
- Implement the more detailed risk assessment matrix for identified formats to support preservation planning

This work has highlighted the need to build on the functional model with more detail needed on essential characteristics for common record types

The team want to expand on the use of the matrix to include evaluating potential new formats for migration, digitisation or transfers advice

File Format Matrix: The Format Matrix was designed for more in-depth evaluation of formats that will support digital archiving decision making. This may include, advice to government agencies, digitisation and preferred formats as well as preservation planning or potential migration for preservation. The matrix currently includes four different sections for assessment: Technical, Documentation, Render Pathway and Essential Characteristics

4.1. Key for Risk Assessment

Use the colour key below to assess risk, select the relevant color for each category to determine the risk level

	Low Impact	Medium Impact	High Impact
File Name	Green	Yellow	Red
File Extension	Green	Yellow	Red
File Content	Green	Yellow	Red
File Size	Green	Yellow	Red
File Location	Green	Yellow	Red
File Date	Green	Yellow	Red
File Type	Green	Yellow	Red
File Format	Green	Yellow	Red
File Version	Green	Yellow	Red
File Metadata	Green	Yellow	Red
File Security	Green	Yellow	Red
File Access	Green	Yellow	Red
File Migration	Green	Yellow	Red
File Preservation	Green	Yellow	Red
File Risk	Green	Yellow	Red
File Status	Green	Yellow	Red
File Type	Green	Yellow	Red
File Version	Green	Yellow	Red
File Metadata	Green	Yellow	Red
File Security	Green	Yellow	Red
File Access	Green	Yellow	Red
File Migration	Green	Yellow	Red
File Preservation	Green	Yellow	Red
File Risk	Green	Yellow	Red
File Status	Green	Yellow	Red

Key for the digital format risk assessment matrix

File Format Register: this excel document collates data from multiple collection across the archives to assist preservation staff to monitor format prevalence and type as well as assess for areas of high risk that may require action. It contains data about formats including PRONOM PUID and submissions to PRONOM, prevalence in different systems and digital record type to assist preservation planning. Some of this functionality is designed to make up for current system gaps that are being iteratively improved.

Sections of the file format register including category impact and prevalence of content

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**SAES: Secure Access Examination System